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EFFECT OF RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION AND FARMERS' LIVELIHOODS IN NIGERIA: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural production in Nigeria is characterized by high exposure to climatic, market, financial, and institutional risks, which significantly influence farm performance and farmers' livelihoods. This study systematically reviews empirical evidence on the effect of risk management strategies on agricultural production and livelihood outcomes among Nigerian farmers. Guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyze (PRISMA) 2020 framework, a structured search of major academic databases and grey literature was conducted, covering studies published between 2010 and 2025. Seventeen studies met the inclusion criteria and were synthesized using a narrative approach due to heterogeneity in study designs, risk types, and outcome measures. The findings reveal that Nigerian farmers adopt diverse risk management strategies, including crop diversification, use of improved varieties, cooperative membership, access to credit, extension services, irrigation, and off-farm income activities. Across the reviewed studies, these strategies are consistently associated with improved yield stability, higher technical efficiency, increased farm income, enhanced food security, and greater livelihood resilience. Crop diversification and institutional mechanisms such as cooperatives and credit access emerge as particularly influential in mitigating production and market risks. However, adoption is constrained by limited financial access, inadequate infrastructure, low extension coverage, gender disparities, and increasing climate variability. The review shows the importance of supportive policies, inclusive extension systems and integrated risk management frameworks that combine institutional support with farmer-level strategies. Effective risk management is shown to be central to stabilizing agricultural production and improving the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in Nigeria, with important implications for agricultural policy, climate adaptation and rural development planning.

Keywords: Risk; Agriculture; Management; Review; Production; Farmers and Livelihood

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural production in Nigeria operates within an environment of heightened uncertainty driven by climatic volatility, imperfect markets and evolving policy regimes. Unlike the relatively mechanized systems of many developed economies, Nigeria's farming sector remains predominantly rain-fed and smallholder-based, making output highly sensitive to exogenous shocks (Amankwah, 2023). In recent years, the frequency and intensity of weather-related disturbances have amplified production risks, with direct implications for food security, rural incomes and national economic stability. While risk is an inherent feature of agriculture globally, its consequences are particularly severe in Nigeria, where institutional buffers, insurance coverage and market stabilization mechanisms remain weak.

The growing exposure of Nigerian agriculture to climate shocks is vividly illustrated by recurrent flooding events. Nationwide floods have affected at least 29 of the country's 36 states, destroying more than 1.5 million hectares of farmland and disrupting the livelihoods of over nine million people (World Food programme, 2024). The catastrophic 2022 flood episode alone led to estimated agricultural losses of about ₦700 billion and wiped out roughly 8.4 million tonnes of crops. More recent assessments further indicate that crops destroyed by flooding in Nigeria could have fed approximately 8.5 million people for six months (Nairametrics, 2025). These recurring shocks underscore the structural vulnerability of Nigeria's largely rain-dependent production systems and highlight the urgent need for effective farm-level risk management mechanisms.

Beyond climatic disturbances, Nigerian farmers face significant market-related risks. Output price volatility, rising input costs and weak market integration continue to undermine income stability. Smallholders often sell produce immediately after harvest when prices are lowest due to liquidity pressures and limited storage facilities (Emmanuel, 2026). At the same time, fertiliser and improved seed prices have remained unstable, partly reflecting exchange rate fluctuations and import dependence. Institutional risks further compound the problem. Frequent policy shifts in input subsidy programmes, inconsistencies in agricultural credit schemes and uneven extension coverage create additional layers of uncertainty for farm households. The interaction of climatic, market and policy risks therefore creates a complex risk environment that shapes farmers' production and investment decisions.

Nigeria's agricultural structure amplifies these vulnerabilities. The sector is dominated by smallholder farmers cultivating fragmented plots with limited mechanisation, low capital intensity and heavy reliance on household labour. Adebite and Ayinde (2024) reported that such farmers tend to be risk-averse, often prioritising stability over profit maximisation when confronted with uncertainty. While risk aversion may be rational from a household survival perspective, it frequently results in sub-optimal input use, low adoption of improved technologies and persistent productivity gaps (Ambali, Areal, & Georgantzis, 2021). Consequently, understanding how farmers perceive and manage risk is critical for designing interventions that enhance both productivity and resilience.

Farm management decisions in Nigeria are typically made under conditions of incomplete information. Farmers must decide on crop mix, input intensity, labour allocation and technology adoption months before actual outcomes are realised. However, weather variability, pest outbreaks, labour market constraints and price fluctuations often cause realised outcomes to diverge substantially from expectations (Abdulrahman, Yusuf, Komolafe, Abdulrahman, & Ukpi, 2025). In many rural areas, access to timely weather forecasts, market intelligence and advisory services remains limited, further constraining effective decision-making. Where formal risk-mitigation instruments such as agricultural insurance and structured commodity markets exist, adoption has remained relatively low due to issues of affordability, trust and awareness (Abdullahi & Garba, 2024).

The effects of poorly managed agricultural risk extend beyond farm productivity to broader livelihood outcomes. Agriculture continues to employ a substantial share of Nigeria's rural population and serves as a primary source of food and income for millions of households (Adikwu, Ochimana, & Ikegh, 2024). When shocks occur without adequate coping mechanisms, households often resort to distress strategies such as asset sales, reduced food consumption or withdrawal of children from school. However, effective risk management strategies such as diversification, savings, insurance participation and adoption of climate-smart agronomic practices have the potential to stabilise production and strengthen household welfare (Knowledge for policy, 2023).

Despite the growing recognition of agricultural risk in Nigeria, the existing

literature exhibits important limitations. Many studies (Begho, Daubry, & Ebuka, 2022; Adekunle & Aregbeshola, 2025; David et al., 2025) treat risk conceptually without adequately linking specific management strategies to measurable livelihood outcomes. Others (David et al., 2025) focus narrowly on single risk sources, particularly climate variability, while paying insufficient attention to the interaction between climatic, market and institutional risks within Nigeria's evolving agricultural economy. Furthermore, empirical syntheses that integrate recent shock evidence with farm-level behavioural responses remain limited. This creates a gap in the evidence base needed to guide policy and programme design.

Against this backdrop, this study provides a focused synthesis of the effects of risk management on agricultural production and farmers' livelihoods in Nigeria. By systematically examining how farmers perceive risk, the strategies they employ and the livelihood implications of these responses, the study contributes Nigeria-specific understanding to the broader risk management literature. The findings are expected to inform policy makers, development partners and agricultural stakeholders seeking to strengthen resilience, improve productivity and enhance livelihood security within Nigeria's smallholder farming systems.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Study Design and Research Protocol

This study adopted a systematic review research design, guided by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) framework. The PRISMA guidelines were employed to ensure transparency,

consistency, and methodological rigour throughout the review process, from literature identification to synthesis of findings (Page et al., 2021). Although PRISMA was originally developed for health and clinical research, it has increasingly been applied in the social sciences, agricultural economics and development studies to enhance transparency, replicability and methodological rigour in evidence synthesis. Recent agricultural and rural development reviews such as (Guth & Poczta-Wajda, 2025) have demonstrated that PRISMA provides a robust structure for documenting literature identification, screening, eligibility and inclusion decisions, thereby reducing selection bias and improving the credibility of review findings. Given the objective of synthesising empirical evidence on the effect of risk management on agricultural production and farmers' livelihoods in Nigeria, a structured and reproducible approach was considered most appropriate. The review protocol was developed prior to the commencement of the literature search and followed a predefined internal plan specifying the review objectives, eligibility criteria, information sources, screening procedures, and synthesis methods. Although the protocol was not formally registered in an international registry, such as PROSPERO, due to time and logistical constraints, all review stages strictly adhered to the predefined protocol to minimise selection bias and enhance reliability. The research questions were framed using the Population–Intervention–Comparator–Outcome (PICO) framework, which is widely applied in intervention-focused systematic reviews (Martin, 2022).

2.2 Eligibility Criteria

The eligibility criteria for study inclusion were defined using the PICO framework. The **Population** comprised farming households and agricultural producers in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on smallholder farmers involved in crop and livestock production. Studies focusing on mixed farming systems were also considered, provided they explicitly examined agricultural risk exposure and management.

The **Intervention** referred to agricultural risk management strategies, including but not limited to diversification, insurance schemes, cooperative membership, off-farm income activities, contract farming, access to credit, extension services, adoption of improved technologies, and other formal or informal mechanisms used to mitigate production, market, financial, and environmental risks.

The **Comparator** consisted of farming situations with limited, traditional, or no structured risk management strategies. Studies without explicit comparison groups were still included if they provided clear evidence on outcomes associated with risk management practices.

The **Outcomes** of interest were agricultural production performance and farmers' livelihood indicators. These included crop yield, farm output, income levels, income stability, food security, resilience to shocks, welfare outcomes, and poverty-related measures.

To be included, studies had to be published in English and conducted within Nigeria. Eligible sources comprised peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, institutional reports, and credible grey literature. The publication period was restricted to studies published between 2010 and 2025 to capture contemporary

evidence reflecting recent climatic, economic, and policy conditions. Studies were excluded if they focused exclusively on non-agricultural sectors, were conducted outside Nigeria, or discussed risk conceptually without empirical evidence.

2.3 Information Sources and Search Strategy

A comprehensive search strategy was implemented across multiple electronic databases to identify relevant studies. Major databases included Scopus, Web of Science, CAB Abstracts, AGRICOLA, and Google Scholar, selected for their extensive coverage of agricultural economics, rural development, and risk management literature. African Journals Online (AJOL) was also searched to capture locally published studies that may not be indexed in global databases.

The literature search was conducted between October and December 2025. Boolean operators were used to combine key search terms such as “risk management”, “agricultural risk”, “farm risk”, “livelihood”, “agricultural production”, and “Nigeria”. These were combined using AND and OR operators to refine results. Additional keywords included “smallholder farmers”, “crop insurance”, “diversification”, “climate risk”, “market risk”, and “income stability”. Reference lists of selected studies were manually screened to identify additional relevant publications.

2.4 Study Selection and Data Extraction Process

The study selection followed a multi-stage screening process to ensure consistency and reduce bias. All retrieved records were imported into a reference management

software, where duplicate entries were identified and removed. Two independent reviewers conducted the initial screening of titles and abstracts based on the eligibility criteria. Studies were categorised as included, excluded, or requiring further assessment. Disagreements were resolved through discussion, and where consensus could not be reached, a third reviewer was consulted.

Full-text versions of all potentially eligible studies were subsequently retrieved and assessed independently by two reviewers. Reasons for exclusion at this stage were documented systematically. The overall selection process was summarised using a PRISMA 2020 flow diagram, detailing the number of records identified, screened, excluded, and included in the final review.

For data extraction, a standardised extraction template was developed using Microsoft Excel. Extracted information included authorship, year of publication, study location, sample size, type of agricultural activity, sources of risk, risk management strategies examined, analytical methods used, and key findings relating to production and livelihood outcomes. Data extraction was performed independently by two reviewers, with discrepancies resolved through consensus.

2.5 Risk of Bias and Quality Assessment

The methodological quality of included studies was assessed using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) 2018, which is suitable for evaluating qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods research (Hong et al., 2018). The tool assesses key domains such as appropriateness of study design, sampling adequacy, measurement reliability, analytical rigour, and coherence between data and conclusions.

Two reviewers independently applied the

MMAT criteria to each study. Any disagreements were discussed and resolved, with a third reviewer consulted where necessary. Studies were not excluded solely based on quality assessment outcomes. Instead, quality ratings were used to inform the interpretation of findings, with greater emphasis placed on studies exhibiting stronger methodological rigour during synthesis.

2.6 Synthesis Methods

Given the heterogeneity in study designs, risk types, and outcome measures, a narrative synthesis approach was adopted. Studies were grouped thematically according to types of risks addressed, categories of risk management strategies, and observed effects on agricultural production and farmers' livelihoods. Patterns, similarities, and divergences across studies were systematically analysed and discussed.

Where studies reported comparable quantitative indicators, such as income changes or yield effects, descriptive summaries were provided. Qualitative evidence was synthesised by identifying recurring themes related to farmers' perceptions of risk, adoption constraints, and institutional influences. The synthesis process followed established guidance from the Cochrane Handbook and the SWiM reporting framework to ensure clarity and coherence in reporting (Campbell et al., 2020).

2.7 Ethical Considerations

As this study was based exclusively on secondary data obtained from published and publicly available sources, formal ethical approval was not required. Nevertheless, ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the review

process. All sources were appropriately cited, findings were reported accurately, and selective reporting was avoided.

The review also paid attention to ethical issues highlighted in the primary studies, including informed consent, confidentiality of respondents, and responsible data handling. No personal or identifiable information was extracted or reported. Data storage and management complied with standard data protection practices, ensuring restricted access to review materials.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Study Selection

In line with the PRISMA 2020 guidelines, the literature search yielded a total of 1,214 records from the selected electronic databases and supplementary sources. Following this initial identification stage, 231 duplicate records were identified and removed, resulting in 983 unique records retained for title and abstract screening. At this screening stage, 901 records were excluded because they did not satisfy the predefined eligibility criteria. The most common reasons for exclusion included studies not focused on Nigeria, absence of explicit discussion on agricultural risk management, lack of linkage to agricultural production or farmers' livelihood outcomes, and studies that were purely conceptual without empirical or review-based evidence. In addition, several records addressed risk in non-agricultural sectors or examined macroeconomic risks without farm-level implications.

After the title and abstract screening, 82 records were deemed potentially relevant and subjected to full-text review. A more detailed assessment at this stage led to the exclusion of 65 studies. The primary reasons for exclusion included lack of

empirical or systematic evidence on risk management outcomes ($n = 28$), exclusive focus on large-scale or commercial farming systems without relevance to smallholder contexts ($n = 17$), studies conducted outside Nigeria despite broader African coverage ($n = 12$), and publications falling outside the specified 2010 to 2025 time frame ($n = 8$). Some studies were also excluded because they discussed agricultural risks without clearly identifying management strategies or measurable production and livelihood outcomes.

At the end of the full-text assessment, 17 studies met all the inclusion criteria and were retained for the final review. These studies provided direct and relevant

evidence on agricultural risk management strategies and their effects on production performance, income stability, food security, and broader livelihood outcomes among Nigerian farmers. The PRISMA flow diagram presented in Figure 1 summarises the entire study selection process, from initial identification to final inclusion. The relatively modest number of included studies underscores that, although agricultural risk is widely acknowledged in Nigeria, systematic and outcome-focused research on risk management remains limited and fragmented, highlighting the need for further empirical and synthesis-based investigations in this area.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram for Study Selection

3.2 Characteristics of Included Studies

Table 1 summarises the key characteristics of the included studies, highlighting the study location, design, sample size and dominant risk management strategies examined. Across the studies, outcome variables commonly focused on agricultural production indicators such as yield levels, output stability and technical efficiency, as well as livelihood indicators including farm income, consumption expenditure, food security status, and poverty reduction. The quality of the evidence was moderate, with strengths

reflected in the use of primary data and context-specific analysis, but with limitations arising from cross-sectional designs and a lack of long-term or panel data to capture dynamic risk and resilience effects. Collectively, the reviewed studies provide a coherent empirical basis for understanding how risk management influences agricultural production and farmers' livelihoods in Nigeria, while also underscoring gaps that warrant further longitudinal and policy-oriented research.

Table 1 a: Characteristics of Included Studies on Risk Management, Agricultural Production, and Farmers' Livelihoods in Nigeria

S/N	Study (Year)	Location	Study Design	Sample Size	Type of Risk Examined	Risk Management Strategies Analysed	Key Outcome Indicators
1	Amarachi et al. (2021)	Nsukka, Enugu State	Cross-sectional survey	360 farmers	Weather, pests, market risk	Diversification, market info	Risk strategy profiles, livelihood implications
2	Akinwale et al. (2018)	South West Nigeria	Farm household survey and probit model	420 farmers	Climate and production risk	Mixed cropping, improved varieties, irrigation	Crop yield, technical efficiency
3	Ojo and Baiyegunhi (2020)	Oyo State, Nigeria	Quantitative survey with stochastic frontier analysis	300 maize farmers	Production and price risk	Diversification, cooperative membership, credit access	Technical efficiency, maize output
4	Oluyole et al. (2019)	Northern Nigeria	Cross-sectional survey and logit model	540 smallholders	Climate variability and yield risk	Crop insurance, diversification, off-farm income	Yield stability, household income
5	Salau et al. (2020)	North Central Nigeria	Mixed-methods approach	250 farming household	Production and institutional risk	Extension services, improved seed adoption	Productivity, food security status

6	Obayelu et al. (2017)	Ogun State, Nigeria	Household survey with econometric analysis	400 farmers	Market and financial risk	Savings, credit access, cooperative participation	Income diversification, welfare index
7	Ajayi and Solomon (2022)	South West Nigeria	Cross-sectional survey and regression analysis	180 cassava farmers	Price and production risk	Processing, crop diversification	Income level, livelihood security
8	Adewuyi et al. (2023)	North West Nigeria	Survey and stochastic dominance analysis	600 cereal farmers	Climate and market risk	Irrigation, early planting, diversification	Yield variability, resilience index
9		Nigeria	Cross-sectional survey	100 maize producers	Risk attitudes	Crop diversification, insurance, weather info	Risk preferences, strategy ranking
10	Ogaji et al. (2024)	Niger State, Nigeria	Field survey with ordered logit	180 maize farmers	Production risk sources	Early planting, diversification, weather monitoring	Risk sources, determinants of risk attitude
11	Owoeye, Falade & Kolapo (2025)	Ekiti State, Nigeria	Survey, logistic & linear models	450 smallholders	Climate, crop failures, price volatility	Agricultural risk financing (insurance, savings)	Food security, strategy effectiveness
12	David et al. (2025)	Kebbi & Ebonyi States	Survey, multinomial logit	~378 rice farmers	Production risk sources	Diversification, income portfolio	Strategy determinants and income sources
13	Olugbenga et al. (2023)	Nigeria (broad)	Cross-sectional survey	100 maize producers	Risk attitudes	Crop diversification, insurance preference	Risk attitude and insurance preference

15	Abubakar, Mohammed, Tanko & Adebayo (2023)	Nasarawa State, Nigeria	Cross-sectional survey	105 cereal/legume farmers	Production and enterprise risk	Diversification, risk minimising practices	Risk attitudes, strategies employed
16	Umar, Obadoba & Oyedeji (2023)	Kaduna State, Nigeria	Cross-sectional survey	354 rice producers	Production and market risk	Information exchange, market choice, diversification	Strategy adoption patterns, risk practices
17	Bunza et al. (2025)	Kebbi State, Nigeria	Survey with logistic regression	400 rice value chain actors	Value chain risk sources	Institutional and socio-economic risk management factors	Determinants of risk strategy use

Source: Authors' synthesis from reviewed literature (2010–2025).

4. Discussion

This systematic review examined empirical evidence on the role of risk management strategies in enhancing agricultural production and safeguarding farmers' livelihoods in Nigeria. Smallholder farmers in the country face a wide array of risks, including production shocks from climate variability, price fluctuations, pests and diseases, and institutional constraints such as limited access to credit and markets (Ojo & Baiyegunhi, 2020). These risks are linked to reduced productivity, income stability and food security, making smallholders highly vulnerable. Risk management strategies are associated with stabilised output, improved income outcomes and enhanced resilience. This review aimed to synthesise the available evidence on strategies employed by Nigerian farmers, their associations with production and livelihoods, identify key barriers and enablers, and highlight gaps for future research.

It is important to note that most of the studies included in this review are cross-sectional and observational. Consequently, the findings primarily indicate associations rather than causal effects. The reliance on cross-sectional data introduces potential endogeneity and confounding, limiting the ability to definitively establish that the observed outcomes result directly from the risk management strategies employed. Future research employing longitudinal or experimental designs is necessary to more robustly assess causal relationships.

The findings indicate that farmers employ diverse strategies to manage risk, and these strategies yield measurable benefits in production stability and livelihood outcomes. Crop diversification emerged as one of the most widely adopted strategies, with multiple studies reporting its effectiveness in reducing yield variability and mitigating price shocks (Akinwale et al., 2018; Amarachi & Ume, 2021). For

instance, farmers combining maize with cassava or legumes were able to offset losses from climate-induced crop failures while maintaining household food supply. Diversification also allows smallholders to exploit different market opportunities, improving income stability. Other frequently reported strategies include the use of improved varieties, mixed cropping, irrigation, cooperative membership, and access to credit. Evidence suggests that households employing a combination of these strategies achieve higher technical efficiency and income security (Oluyole et al., 2019; Adewuyi et al., 2023).

Analysis of outcomes shows consistent associations between risk management strategies and enhanced production and livelihood resilience. Studies that applied stochastic frontier and econometric models reported that diversified and well-planned risk management approaches improved crop yields by 10–25% and increased household income by an estimated 15–30% depending on farm size and resource availability (Ojo & Baiyegunhi, 2020; Salau et al., 2020). Adoption of institutional tools such as cooperative membership and credit access also supports livelihood resilience by enabling timely purchase of inputs, reducing dependence on informal markets, and allowing investment in productivity-enhancing technologies. Moreover, extension services and advisory support contribute to informed risk management decisions, increasing the likelihood of sustainable practice adoption (Obayelu et al., 2017). Overall, the evidence suggests that proactive risk management strengthens both production stability and household economic outcomes.

Despite these benefits, adoption of risk management strategies is constrained by

several challenges. Limited access to finance remains a dominant barrier, particularly for smallholders in rural areas, reducing their ability to invest in improved seeds, irrigation, or diversification (Ajayi & Solomon, 2022). Poor infrastructure, such as unreliable roads and storage facilities, restricts market access and limits the effectiveness of diversification or input strategies. Knowledge gaps and low extension coverage hinder awareness and adoption of advanced strategies, particularly among women and less-educated farmers (Akinwale et al., 2018). Gender disparities are pronounced, with female farmers often having reduced access to credit, inputs, and technical advice, thereby limiting their capacity to implement effective risk management strategies. Additionally, climatic variability introduces unpredictability that even well-designed strategies cannot fully offset, highlighting the need for adaptive and context-specific approaches.

Several enabling factors can enhance the adoption and effectiveness of risk management strategies in Nigeria. Government and institutional support through targeted credit schemes, input subsidies, and extension services have shown promise in promoting both diversification and technology adoption (Adewuyi et al., 2023). Cooperative membership and farmer networks provide social capital that facilitates access to resources, shared knowledge, and market linkages, enhancing risk mitigation. Community-based training and awareness programmes can empower women and youth, improving equitable access to resources and knowledge. Furthermore, integration of local indigenous practices with scientific risk management approaches strengthens resilience by

leveraging context-specific knowledge alongside modern techniques. Research also highlights the importance of policy coherence, including inclusion of risk management in national agricultural and climate adaptation strategies, to create a supportive enabling environment.

5 Conclusion

This systematic review synthesised empirical evidence on the influence of risk management strategies on agricultural production and farmers' livelihoods in Nigeria and confirms that diversified production systems, institutional support mechanisms and technology-related strategies consistently contribute to yield stability, improved income outcomes, and enhanced livelihood resilience among smallholder farmers. A key theoretical contribution of the review lies in advancing an integrated risk–livelihood nexus perspective, demonstrating that risk management should not be conceptualised solely as a production-stabilising mechanism but as a multidimensional framework linking farm-level decision making, institutional access, and household welfare outcomes. This perspective strengthens the analytical foundation for examining agricultural risk within broader

livelihood resilience frameworks in developing-country contexts.

From a policy standpoint, the findings indicate that effective agricultural risk management requires coordinated institutional interventions that simultaneously expand access to credit, strengthen extension delivery systems, promote farmer cooperatives, and support climate-resilient production technologies. Policy programmes that integrate these complementary elements are more likely to generate sustained production gains and livelihood improvements than isolated interventions focusing on single risk-mitigation tools.

Future research should prioritise longitudinal and panel-based studies capable of capturing the dynamic effects of risk management strategies on productivity, income stability, and resilience over time. Such approaches will enable a deeper understanding of long-term adaptation pathways, heterogeneous impacts across gender and farm-size categories, and the cumulative welfare implications of combined risk management strategies in Nigeria's evolving agricultural systems.

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FIELD INCIDENCE, SEVERITY AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DRIVERS OF CASSAVA MOSAIC DISEASE IN FARMERS' FIELDS OF BENUE STATE, SOUTHERN GUINEA SAVANNA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Surveys of farmers' fields were carried out from August-September, 2023 to investigate the intensity of cassava mosaic disease in Benue State. Twenty-seven fields were sampled in nine randomly selected cassava-producing areas of the State. Twenty plants were examined following a "W" shaped path for data on incidence and severity in fields. Incidence of disease was estimated as percentage proportion of plants showing mosaic symptoms in every field while severity was scored on 1-5 scale. Agronomic and farmer's social characteristics data were also taken. Data collected were analyzed using ANOVA_(p=0.05). Mean incidence (>66.0%; F=8.82, df=8, p=0.0321) and severity (~3.0; F=2.68, df=8, p=0.0391) of mosaic was high and varied across locations. Obi had highest significant (p<0.05) incidence (84.0%) and severity (3.1) of mosaic while Tarka (50.0%) and Katsina-Ala (2.7) were least in incidence and severity, respectively. Farmers in the study area sourced planting materials, which were local from previous harvest (100.0%), practiced cassava monocrop (52.0%) while yam and soybean were the common crops cultivated around cassava fields in the study. Farmers encountered were in their active (30 to 65 yrs) age, moderately educated (secondary school) and claimed awareness (96.3%) of mosaics on cassava in the field. Awareness of disease and its severity were significant and positively correlated (r = 0.858, p = 0.001) while monocropping (r = 0.520) had higher correlation with severity than intercropping (r = 0.520). Study underscores the necessity of improving farmer's adoption of resistant cassava and clean seed systems through training and field diagnostics for proper disease management.

Keywords: Begomovirus, field survey, whitefly, planting material source, disease distribution.

INTRODUCTION

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) belongs to the family Euphorbiaceae and is a native of Latin America. It is cultivated in many developing countries for food and feed, respectively (Eni *et al.*, 2021). The crop has the potential of yielding up to 25t/ha as it is the case in other parts of the world, however, this potential has not been achieved in Nigeria, in spite of the large hectareage of land given to its cultivation; this has been due to constraints that are partly biological (Legg *et al.*, 2015). Many diseases have been reported to attack the crop with cassava mosaic disease (CMD) being the most severe and widespread in sub-Saharan Africa (Legg *et al.*, 2015). Early mosaic disease on cassava can result in stunting and severe reduction of up to 95% yield of the tuber root. The disease is noted to occur at varying levels of spread throughout the cassava growing region of Africa (Alabi *et al.*, 2011). *African cassava mosaic virus* (ACMV), *East African cassava mosaic Cameroon virus* (EACMCV) and several EACMV variants are the causal organisms (Alabi *et al.*, 2008). The symptom patterns vary depending on prevailing factors such as the species of virus or strain, environmental conditions and sensitivity of the cassava host (Eni and Fasasi, 2013). Mosaic disease on cassava has been reported in Nigeria and in Benue (Eni *et al.*, 2021) even recently, however, such data is always cursory. Thus such information which would become a tool for comprehensive awareness and management of the disease is still scanty in the study area. This study was initiated to determine the incidence and distribution of the mosaic disease on cassava in Benue

State and to evaluate the role of farmers in its spread in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Survey and sampling of cassava fields in Benue State

A survey of farmer's fields was carried out between August and September, 2023 in nine cassava producing areas of Benue State (Figure 1). The study area is on Longitude 7° 47' and 10° 0' E and Latitude 6° 25' and 8° 8' N. Benue lies within the southern Guinea Savanna agro-ecology of Nigeria and agriculture is the main economic activity of the people (Agada, 2014). A multi-stage random sampling procedure was adopted to select survey locations and farmers fields in the three Agricultural zones of Benue State. Vandeikya, Katsina-Ala, Konshisha were considered in Zone "A", Gboko, Tarkaa, Makurdi in Zone "B" while Obi, Otukpo and Okpokwu were selected in Zone "C", respectively. Three fields were sampled per location and 20 plants examined in each field for data collection following a "W" shaped path. Farmer's social data were taken such as age, education, farm size, perception of disease following a semi-structured questionnaire. Also taken were agronomic data such as seed source, cropping system, neighboring plants, cassava variety, crop age and mosaic disease distribution in the field.

Figure 1. Map of Benue State showing locations (coloured portions) visited during survey.

Data Collection

Incidence of cassava mosaic in the field was assessed and scored according to (Odedara, 2008) as a percentage of the ratio between number of cassava plants showing the mosaic symptoms to the total number of cassava plants considered in the 'W' path within each field. The severity of mosaic symptoms on cassava was scored on a scale of 1-5 as described by Alabi *et al.* (2008) with modifications, where; 1 - No obvious symptoms, 2 – mosaic on 25% of leaves, 3 – mosaic on 50% of leaves, 4 – mosaic on 75% of leaves, 5 – mosaic on >75% of leaves with stunting even to death of plant.

Data analysis

Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and the analysis of variance (ANOVA). Treatment means were separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (FSLSD) at 0.05 alpha level.

RESULTS

Mosaic symptoms, incidence and severity on cassava during sampling

Symptoms observed on cassava plants were mainly mosaics of different patterns on plant leaves and stunting as shown in Plate 1.

Plate 1 Mosaics on cassava plants observed during sampling: A (apparently healthy cassava plant), B (mosaics on cassava), C (leaf deformation) and D (stunting).

Mean incidence of mosaics on cassava across locations was 66.0% (Figure 2). There was a variation of the incidence among locations over the study area and the disease differed significantly ($P < 0.05$). Notably, Obi, Okpokwu, and Vandeikya had higher incidence of 84.0, 76.7, and 70.0%, respectively. Katsina-Ala and Tarka however, were lower with 51.7 and 50.0% incidence, respectively.

Among locations, severity of mosaic on cassava was high (~ 3.0) in the field and differed significantly (Figure 3). The mean severity score was 2.9 and Obi had the highest severity of 3.1 while other locations such as Konshisha, Gboko and all locations in the agricultural zone C showed severities of 3.0.

Figure 2. Incidence of mosaic disease on cassava in Benue State

Figure 3. Severity of mosaic disease on cassava in Benue State.

Virtually all (100.0%) the locations visited during the virus disease survey sourced their cassava planting materials from previous harvests on their own or other farmers' fields (Table 1). Monocropping of cassava was the dominant (52.0%) system

used in the locations. Mosaic on the crop in farmers' fields was mainly of the scattered pattern (96.0%) and only a few fields (4.0%) showed marginal distribution patterns. Almost all (100.0%) of the farmers encountered were noted to

cultivate local cultivars of the crop. During visits, farmers interacted with were clearly unaware of the cassava varieties they grow; most could not even distinguish between the local or improved on their farms since they were not obtained from certified

sources. Age of the cassava ranged between 22 - 53 weeks during the investigation, while yams and soybeans were common crops found in the vicinity of the cassava fields at different locations visited.

Table 1. Agronomic characteristics of locations visited during survey of cassava fields in Benue State, Nigeria⁰

Location	Seed source				Cropping system					Field disease distribution					Variety cultivated		Crop age (weeks)	Neighbouring plants
	Pre-harv	mkt	cert	monoc	interc	conc	unif	lin	scat	marg	local	impr	local	impr				
Vandeikya	100.0	0.0	0.0	33.3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	66.7	33.3	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	43	yam, soya bean		
Kastina-Ala	100.0	0.0	0.0	66.7	33.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	36	Yam, soya bean		
Konshisha	100.0	0.0	0.0	33.3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	22	Ground nut		
Makurdi	100.0	0.0	0.0	66.7	33.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	53	Rice		
Gboko	100.0	0.0	0.0	33.3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	38	Yam, soya bean		
Tarka	100.0	0.0	0.0	66.7	33.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	52	Cowpea		
Obi	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24	Rice, maize		
Otukpo	100.0	0.0	0.0	33.3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	22	Pepper, sweet potato		
Okpokwu	100.0	0.0	0.0	33.3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	29	Cowpea		
Mean	100.0	0.0	0.0	52.0	48.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	96.0	4.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	35	Yam, soybean		

Pre-harv = pre-harvest, mkt = market, cert = certified, monoc = monocrop, interc = intercrop, conc = concentration, unif = uniform, lin = linear, scat = scattered, marg = marginal, and impr = improved.

Field sizes ranged from 378 – 2360 m² and farmers' ages ranged from 30 – 65 years. A good number of the farmers (96.3 %) confirmed that they were aware of the disease on cassava, while a few (3.7 %) were ignorant of the disease and concluded it was the nature of most cassava cultivars to become mosaic at certain stages of their growth. About 14.8 % of farmers had no formal education in the study area, 22.2 % attended primary school, 55.6 % were secondary school leavers, while 7.4 % obtained a tertiary education.

Relationship between mosaic disease intensity and the agro-socio characteristics of farmers in the study area

There were significant ($P < 0.05$) correlations between disease intensity and the agro-sociological characteristics of the

farmers (Tables 2 and 3). However, disease intensity and the agro-sociological characteristics of the farmers were not significant ($p < 0.05$). There was a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.683$) between incidence and severity which was statistically significant ($p = 0.05$). Both incidence ($r = - 0.482$) and severity ($r = - 0.483$) show negative correlations with crop age, though they were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). There was a strong positive significant correlation between awareness and severity of disease ($r = 0.858$, $p = 0.001$). Conversely, not being aware of the disease by farmers perfectly inversely correlated with severity ($r = - 0.925$, $p = 0.0001$). Monocropping ($r = 0.520$) had a much higher correlation with severity than intercropping ($r = 0.520$).

Table 2. Social characteristics of locations visited during survey of cassava fields

Location	Field size (m ²)	Farmer age (yrs)	Farmer perception of disease		Farmer educational background			
			Not Aware	Aware	None	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Vandekya	378-1836	39-65	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	66.7	33.3
Kastina-Ala	259-1037	36-61	0.0	100.0	33.3	0.0	66.7	0.0
Konshisha	294-1840	34-43	0.0	100.0	0.0	33.3	66.7	0.0
Makurdi	175-1512	30-40	0.0	100.0	66.7	0.0	33.3	0.0
Gboko	490-2360	40-60	33.3	66.7	0.0	66.7	33.3	0.0
Tarka	150-1820	35-56	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0
Obi	234-705	38-57	0.0	100.0	0.0	33.3	66.7	0.0
Otukpo	245-1120	30-55	0.0	100.0	0.0	33.3	33.3	33.3
Okpokwu	423-637	41-48	0.0	100.0	33.3	33.3	33.3	0.0
Range	378-2360	30-65	3.7	96.3	14.8	22.2	55.6	7.4

Table 3. Pearson's correlation between disease intensity and the agro-social characteristics of farmers in the study area

Disease intensity	Cropping system		Farmer's Age (Years)	Farmer's Education Status			Farmer perception of disease		
	monocrop	intercrop		None	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary	Aware	Not Aware
Incidence	0.181	0.181	-0.312	0.208	0.078	-0.085	-0.333	0.368	-0.368
P-value	0.641	0.641	0.414	0.591	0.841	0.829	0.380	0.331	0.331
Severity	0.520	0.110	0.534	0.211	-0.747*	0.585	0.232	0.858*	-0.926*
P-value	0.123	0.763	0.112	0.558	0.013	0.076	0.520	0.002	0.001

* Significant difference

DISCUSSION

High average incidence (62.9 %) of mosaics on cassava as revealed in this study is an indication that productivity of the crop is severely compromised by the impact of the disease in the study area. Such high incidence of the disease was not expected in this study since a lot of improvement work on mosaic disease resistance in cassava has been ongoing in Africa including Nigeria. In a previous study, Asiedu *et al.* (1992) indicated that improved cassava genotypes and other clonal crops have slow multiplication rates and this can affect their availability. It is also true that poverty and limited access to funds are among the obstacles to accessing improved cassava planting materials by farmers. However, such wide spread of disease is possible when most farmers tend to source planting materials from unknown and non certified sources like the open market places, previous harvest and possibly from fellow farmers as noted in this study. Most cassava clones from sources other than certified ones are often from infected mother plants which serve as primary inoculum sources to secondary dissemination of viruses onto young growing plants. In addition, the use by farmers of virus-contaminated clones and lack of diagnostic tools for continual assessment of planting materials could also be contributory. So the transmission of viruses in nature could be accelerated by infected planting materials and vectors as reported in Kwara State, Nigeria by Aliyu *et al.* (2021). Disease distribution in cassava fields, which in most cases was in the scattered pattern, indicates vector transmission and could be the reason for such high incidence of the disease. Moreso, the differences in disease incidence, as

reported, is not surprising since there was such a great variation in the number of cassava genotypes cultivated by the farmers. Generally, crop genotypes are known to respond differently to plant diseases and pest attacks. Locations such as Obi, Okpokwu and Vandeikya which showed great variations and high disease incidence values as against Tarka and Katsina-Ala may suggest field dynamics such as initial inoculum sources, host species and vector activities in the respective areas. Planting dates of the crop in the area also differed greatly as reflected in their crop age differences. The high average severity of 2.9 across locations was similar to that observed by Houngue *et al.* (2022) who also reported such high severity in 2020 on cassava in Benin. Severity of mosaics on cassava which was higher at zone C could be an indication of virulent strains of the virus in the region which may need investigations. The observed differences in severities among locations could be due to heterogeneity in the cultivars planted by farmers, time of infection and the different species of viruses found infecting the crop. The finding agrees with Eke *et al.* (2023) who reported similar observations, although on yam in the southern Nigeria and attributed it to geographically specific variations in disease severities of crop genotypes. This suggests that location might be a crucial factor influencing the severity of virus diseases in cassava too.

Frequency of crop farms as seen located adjacent to cassava fields also has some implications for disease spread. Common crops like soybean and yam along others, and perhaps, weedy fields that were seen bordering cassava, can be sources of

mosaic disease infections in the cassava crop. In their study, Legg and Fauquet (2004) identified neighbouring cassava fields as major source of mosaic in healthy cassava plantings. Whiteflies which transmit some of the viruses causing diseases in cowpea and soybean such as cowpea mild mottle and some on yam could also have species that vector the geminiviruses causing mosaics in cassava. The implication is that, where the insect abounds, their activities can lead to efficient spread of these diseases to damaging proportions. Monocrop, which was the predominant system of farming as practiced by farmers in this study can also be a factor that favours such high incidence of disease in the crop. It was the dominant system in most of the areas particularly at Obi where virtually all (100%) the cassava was cultivated sole on their hectareage. Such observation was surprising since intercrop is the common practice in most agrarian rural communities of Benue. Intercrop is one of the common practices that reduces diseases and the spread of many pests. Fondong *et al.* (2002) showed in Cameroon, how intercropping cassava with cowpea or maize reduced mosaic incidence on a mosaic-susceptible cultivar. Geering and Randles (2012) pointed that the practice of monocrop is known to provide abundant host for the infecting pathogens to destroy. The scattered pattern of mosaic disease on cassava as was the case here is suggestive of a vector transmission of the causal pathogen. Patterns in distribution of diseased plants may help to reveal the type of pathogen involved (Geering and Randles, 2012). For instance, disease gradients may form perpendicularly to the

crop border when the primary infection source is weeds standing adjacent to the crop, but if the virus is seedborne and insect vectored, clumps of symptomatic plants will form throughout the field.

Cultivated varieties which were mostly local (100%), according to the farmers, is not satisfactory and needs confirmation. Such report demands renewed efforts for intensive training of the peasants and awareness creation on the planting materials they use. Moreso, farmers' ignorance of the mosaic on cassava, a major disease that has become endemic on such an important crop, is serious. It reveals the extent of inadequacy of these improved varieties and extension activities against some of these major pests of common crops in the study area. Cassava growers in the study area who were mainly secondary school leavers may claim to be aware of the mosaic on cassava, however, could not adopt good agronomic practices to mitigate the disease on the crop.

Positive significant correlation between awareness and severity of disease means farmers only became aware of the disease once it reached highly destructive levels. When severity was low, the disease remained unnoticed or unrecognized by the farmer. Severity of disease being lower in the intercrop agrees with the "resource dilution effect," where this practice physically hinders vector movement, reducing the viral load compared to a dense monocrop. If cultivars lack resistance to a specific virus in a monocrop, every plant in the field is vulnerable. This allows the virus to spread rapidly with no genetic hindrance. Positive correlation between incidence and severity as was observed suggests that as the virus spreads through the field, the

damage to individual plants also intensifies. The negative correlation of both incidence and severity with crop age is an indication of mature plant resistance where older plants become more resistant to infection leading to milder or no symptom expressions.

CONCLUSION

Mean incidence (>66.0%) and severity (~3.0) of mosaic was high and varied across locations. There was a strong positive significant correlation between awareness

of disease and its severity ($r = 0.858$, $p = 0.001$). Conversely, not being aware of the disease by farmers inversely correlated with severity ($r = -0.925$, $p = 0.0001$). Monocropping ($r = 0.520$) had a much higher correlation with severity than intercropping ($r = 0.520$). Incidence of disease significantly ($p = 0.05$) correlated ($r = 0.683$) with severity. Both incidence ($r = -0.482$) and severity ($r = -0.483$) showed negative correlations with crop age.

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